

ADVANCED THERMOPLASTIC HONEYCOMB CORES: EFFICIENCY GAINS THROUGH COEXTRUDED FOAMED CELL WALLS IN SANDWICH STRUCTURES

Gregor Jesse¹, Friedrich Zerling², Robert Zarnekow², Jochen Pflug², Robert Böhm¹

¹Faculty of Engineering, Leipzig University of Applied Sciences (HTWK Leipzig)
P.O. Box 30 11 66, Karl-Liebknecht-Straße 134, 04277 Leipzig, Germany
Email: gregor.jesse@htwk-leipzig.de, robert.boehm@htwk-leipzig.de,
web page: <https://www.htwk-leipzig.de/>

²Research and Development, ThermHex Waben GmbH
Merseburger Straße 235, 06130 Halle (Saale), Germany
Email: friedrich.zerling@thermhexas.com, web page: <https://thermhexas.com/en>

Keywords: Honeycomb, Thermoplastics, Sandwich, Foams, Buckling, Mechanical properties, FEA

ABSTRACT

As part of the research project “ExSaZell – Efficiency and Performance Enhancement of Thermoplastic Honeycomb Cores through Innovative, Extrusion-Based, Foamed Cellular Wall Systems with Sandwich Structure”, an advanced three-layer cellular wall concept was developed in collaboration of ThermHex, Kunststoff-Zentrum Leipzig (KUZ), and HTWK Leipzig. This approach utilizes the co-extrusion of polypropylene into a multi-layer flat film, followed by continuous thermoforming into honeycomb cores. The resulting cell walls consist of two dense outer layers and a foamed, lower-density inner layer. This structured wall design enables significant improvements in mechanical performance, particularly under compressive loads, while maintaining a constant core density. The integration of a foamed middle layer reduces the overall material mass and increases the effective wall thickness, thereby enhancing buckling resistance, a critical parameter for honeycomb core performance under compressive and shear stresses. Initial industrial trials demonstrated an increase of 21.8% in flatwise compressive strength compared to a conventional monolithic thermoplastic core of equivalent density. The internal structuring was achieved via the targeted addition of a chemical blowing agent and nucleating agent into the base polymer of the inner layer. The concept development and industrial trials conducted by ThermHex were supported by nonlinear finite element analyses (FEA) from HTWK Leipzig and morphological as well as mechanical testing by KUZ Leipzig. The results underline the potential of this sandwich cell wall concept to replace traditional honeycomb core materials in lightweight applications, offering both economic and ecologic advantages through improved resource efficiency, recyclability, and production cost reductions.

INTRODUCTION

The global demand for transport services, whether by air, land, or water, continues to grow [1]. The automotive industry is currently one of the fastest-growing sectors, and this growth is accompanied by an increasing demand for lightweight components [2]. In 2018 alone, 95 million light vehicles were sold worldwide, and this number is expected to rise to 110 million units per year by 2025 [1], [3]. This sustained expansion in the transport sector, however, leads to significant energy consumption and increasing emissions of greenhouse gases, particularly carbon dioxide (CO₂) [1], [2], [4].

To address these challenges and enhance fuel efficiency, vehicle lightweighting is a crucial strategy [5]. Studies indicate that reducing vehicle mass by 10% not only lowers raw material consumption but also cuts car fuel consumption by between 6% to 8% [4]. Every 100 kg removed from a motor vehicle reduces CO₂ emissions by 9 grams per kilometer [2]. For Battery Electric Vehicles (BEVs), the specific consumption saving achievable through 100 kg mass reduction, known as the Energy Reduction Value (ERV), ranges from 0.47 to 1.17 kWh/(100 km × 100 kg), with larger vehicles and more dynamic driving cycles exhibiting higher ERV values [6]. Lightweighting also offers advantages beyond raw material and fuel efficiency [2], such as improved energy efficiency, reduced noise, vibration, and harshness (NVH) [1], and enhanced energy absorption capabilities [3], [5]. Furthermore, lighter materials like aluminum absorb impact better than steel in accidents. Vehicle weight is identified as the most significant factor influencing fuel consumption, accounting for approximately 70% to 75% of total fuel use [2], [4]. For instance, a 30% mass reduction on the body-in-white (BIW) structure of a typical compact car (e.g. Volkswagen Golf) over a lifetime road performance of 150,000 km can lead to fuel savings of around 398 liters (equivalent to ~998 kg CO₂ savings). This implies a saving of approximately 0.3 L/100 km for each car [5]. Overall, studies suggest that a total vehicle weight reduction of up to 12.6% can be achieved, which translates to a CO₂ emission reduction of 25.2 grams per kilometer [4].

In this context, sandwich structures have emerged as a prevalent method for replacing traditional, heavier materials. A typical sandwich structure comprises two solid, force-absorbing face sheets and a lightweight core material that keeps these face sheets separated. This design allows for achieving high mass-specific bending stiffness, strength, and optimal fatigue resistance, while simultaneously reducing the overall weight and cost of the component [7]. Sandwich panels can also be formed into complex shapes, enabling significant component consolidation and simplifying manufacturing processes [3], [5]. Their applications span from floors for heavy-duty trailers and air cargo containers [7], [8] to components for electric vehicles, including vehicle floors and exterior panels [1], [8], [9].

The core of a sandwich structure plays a critical role in the overall mechanical performance of the component, as it spaces the face sheets apart and primarily withstands shear and compressive forces [1]. Honeycomb cores are particularly interesting due to their excellent strength-to-weight ratio and good sound and thermal insulation properties [1], [10]. Various materials are used for honeycomb cores, including paper honeycomb, polypropylene (PP) honeycomb, aluminum honeycomb, and phenolic Nomex aramid fiber honeycomb [1], [9], [10]. It is important to note, however, that most "conventional" sandwich cores (such as traditional honeycomb, wood, or foam) generally contribute only marginally to the overall bending stiffness of the structure, serving primarily as low-density spacers [10].

Despite their shared classification as "honeycomb cores", significant differences exist in the properties and application areas of various materials. Nomex aramid fiber honeycomb, for instance, is extremely lightweight, non-metallic, and offers a unique profile of properties including a high strength-to-weight ratio, toughness, corrosion, fatigue, and impact resistance, as well as fire resistance and good dielectric and thermal insulation characteristics [10]. These superior properties make Nomex suitable for high-performance applications, such as airplane secondary components, but carry an extremely high carbon footprint and can only be calcinated at the end of lifecycle [10]. In contrast, thermoplastic honeycomb cores are characterized by efficient production techniques, their good flexibility and ease of formability, making them more cost-effective and adaptable for automotive applications like electric car floors [9]. Paper honeycomb, known for its low-cost raw material, compressibility during conversion, and low transportation cost, finds wide application in flat commodity products and packaging applications [1].

The selection of the appropriate honeycomb core material thus heavily depends on the specific application, performance requirements, and economic considerations. While the advantages of high-performance honeycombs like Nomex are undeniable in specialized fields, a key challenge for the automotive industry lies in developing cost-effective yet high-performing honeycomb solutions that meet the demands of mass production and optimally define and utilize the specific role of the honeycomb core in the overall bending stiffness of the sandwich structure.

Figure 1: Honeycomb and foam cores in density dependent compression strength [11]

Conventional methods for producing sandwich components are hardly suitable for mass production due to their time and cost. To overcome this, the "ThermHex" honeycomb production process was developed and patented by EconCore N.V., which enables continuous in-line production of thermoplastic honeycomb cores [12]. This technology is applied in industrial scale by EconCore's daughter company ThermHex Waben GmbH in Germany.

Figure 2: Continuous production of thermoplastic honeycomb sandwich panels [12].

Unlike stepwise batch methods, all production steps take place on a single line, starting with the extrusion of a flat film, followed by rotational vacuum forming, folding, laminating, and cutting [12], [13].

This inline efficiency allows for the production of over more than a million square meters of honeycomb cores per year at speeds of up to 10 meters per minute and cost advantages of more than 20% vs. traditional PP cores [12]. The inline-lamination of face sheets from thermoplastic tape laminates during honeycomb core production also enables the manufacturing of sandwich panels for large-scale series production with short cycle times. ThermHex honeycomb cores find wide application, for example in truck bodies and automotive interiors [12].

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE AND INVESTIGATED VARIANTS

A significant innovation in cell wall structure is being pursued in the research project "ExSaZell - Efficiency and performance enhancement of thermoplastic honeycomb cores through innovative, extrusion-based, foamed cellular wall systems with sandwich structure", a collaboration of Thermhex, Kunststoff-Zentrum Leipzig and HTWK Leipzig. The main interest of this research lies in further substructuring the cell wall via co-extrusion. A recurring problem in sandwich structures is the stability failure (buckling) of the cell walls oriented perpendicular to the face sheets under compressive and shear loads. An increase in buckling stiffness at constant weight and identical honeycomb core material is only possible through further structuring of the cell walls themselves.

The project's core innovation involves designing the honeycomb cell walls themselves in a sandwich construction consisting of a layered A-B-A cross sectional substructure. Here, the individual cell walls consist of a core layer (B) with lower density and outer face layers (A) with higher stiffness. PP serves as the material basis, where the individual layers, although chemically homogeneous, can vary through compounding or additivation to achieve specific properties. This allows for the use of high-strength PP homopolymers (PPH) or reinforced PP in the outer layers and lighter PP copolymers (PPC) in the inner layer. The subsequent crucial step for further density reduction and property enhancement is foaming the mid-layer (B) of the cell wall. This is expected to enable a weight-specific increase in the mechanical properties of the honeycomb core by up to 25%.

Figure 3: Multi-layer cell wall approach

The project primarily investigates three variants of cell wall structuring:

1. **Mono layer (reference):** This represents the current state of the art, where the cell walls consist of a homogenized polypropylene compound. This variant is characterized by good mechanical properties and efficient production.
2. **Phase separation:** The goal is a complete demixing of the components, enabling higher weight-specific properties through the use of stiffer/stronger materials in the outer layers and tougher materials in the core layer. This allows for gradients in stiffness and density.
3. **Foamed mid-layer:** In this variant, the density of the core layer (B) is reduced by foaming. This enables a greater cell wall thickness at constant weight and thus leads to increased buckling stiffness and better specific properties of the honeycomb core.

NUMERICAL MODELING

For the Finite Element Analysis (FEA) of honeycomb structures, the unit cell approach was employed in Ansys, leveraging the inherent regular and periodic pattern of hexagonal cell cores. This method significantly simplifies the model by considering only a single hexagonal unit cell, including its adjacent cell walls. The modeling was performed using “SOLSH190” Solid Structural Shell elements, allowing for a parametrically designed model with flexible adjustment of cell wall height, the distance between cell walls, the cell angle, and the thickness ratio of L-walls to W-walls. To enable a comprehensive material investigation, each cell wall was divided into two outer elements enclosing one middle element. This subdivision allowed for the free selection of mechanical properties for the outer and inner layers, as well as the mass fraction between two different materials.

This simulation approach enabled a detailed investigation of various material configurations. As for the reference variant, a monolayer honeycomb core was established where both outer and inner material layers were assigned identical mechanical properties, representing the homogeneous material mixture of the current production's PPH and PPC. The second variant was designed as a phase-separated honeycomb core, specifically assigning PPH properties to the outer layers and PPC properties to the inner layers of the cell walls. This distinction facilitates the analysis of the mechanical response of a heterogeneous material distribution. Furthermore, the model accounted for the foaming of PPC by treating it as a homogenized material with an effective 22.5% reduction of its original mechanical properties, reflecting the impact of the foaming process. It's important to note that the mechanical properties of both PPH and PPC materials were determined through tensile testing of the corresponding virgin materials, which was carried out by KUZ Leipzig. For the numerical model, a “Bilinear Isotropic Hardening” (BISO) material model was utilized, incorporating a tangential modulus of 17.2 MPa (see Table 1).

Figure 4: Unit-Cell with boundary conditions

To optimize computational efficiency for the nonlinear buckling analysis, the inherent X and Y axis symmetry of the honeycomb core allowed for the simulation of a quarter-section of the structure (see Figure 4). Specific boundary conditions were applied to represent the core's behavior under compressive loading: The bottom nodes were fixed to prevent any free translations or rotations, ensuring a stable base. Conversely, the nodes on the opposing (top) side were designated as "one-dimensional displacement nodes," constraining their movements in the X and Y directions, along with rotations about each axis, thereby permitting translation only along the Z-axis. Frictional contact was implemented between the cell walls to prevent unrealistic sliding or interpenetration during deformation. The nonlinear buckling analysis was then conducted by applying a displacement of 10^{-3} mm in the negative Z-direction to these top nodes.

Engineering constant		Polypropylene Homopolymer (PPH)	Polypropylene Copolymer (PPC)	Polypropylene Copolymer (foamed)
ρ	[g/cm ³]	1.03	0.9	0.6975
E	[MPa]	1750	1440	1116
ν_{12}	–	0.3	0.3	0.3
K	[MPa]	1408	1200	930
G	[MPa]	650	554	430
σ	[MPa]	36	27	21
E_t	[MPa]	17.2	17.2	17.2

Table 1: Mechanical properties of PPC and PPH (virgin material)

MANUFACTURING AND MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERIZATION

ThermHex, leveraging its established production capabilities, can realize all three variants investigated in this research project. For the reference variant, the manufacturing process is straightforward. A single extruder is sufficient to melt the PP granulate. This molten material is then extruded through a dedicated die to form a PP foil, which is subsequently folded into the honeycomb core structure on the production line. The production of the phase-separated variant requires a more advanced setup. A second "co-extruder" is integrated into the process, allowing for the separate melting of two distinct material mixtures: one for the outer layer (Layer A) and another for the inner layer (Layer B). A specialized extrusion die, featuring a three-layered feedblock, then co-extrudes these materials simultaneously to create the desired three-layered foil. Finally, the foamed variant is achieved by incorporating a chemical foaming agent into the polypropylene granulate used for the inner layer. The foaming agent type and concentration were selected after an empirical benchmarking study of various combinations of different blowing and nucleating agents as well as their respective concentrations in a pre-investigation by ThermHex and KUZ. The blowing agent decomposes within the extruder, releasing gas. While this gas remains dissolved under pressure inside the extruder, upon exiting the die, a sudden pressure drop causes it to expand rapidly under the formation of gas bubbles, creating the desired cellular structure that is then fixed as the extrudate cools. To validate the desired geometrical and morphological aspects of the produced honeycomb core variants, X-Ray Computed Tomography (CT) scans were performed. CT scanning was chosen due to its ability to non-destructively visualize internal structures and confirm the distinct three-layer configuration of the honeycomb core, allowing clear differentiation of the layers through the material. This method also offered significant advantages in specimen preparation and contrast resolution compared to alternative techniques like optical microscopy, streamlining the validation process.

Figure 5: Schematic representation of coextrusion die system (left) and computed tomography for morphology assessment of produced specimens

EXPERIMENTAL MECHANICAL TESTING

Mechanical properties of each variant were evaluated using 100x100 mm² specimens tested under ASTM C365 conditions. This standard test method, officially titled "Standard Test Method for Flatwise Compressive Properties of Sandwich Cores," defines the procedure for measuring the flatwise compressive strength and modulus of core materials used in sandwich structures. Essentially, it assesses the load a core can withstand when compressed perpendicular to its surface (flatwise), thereby simulating the stresses sandwich cores experience in real-world applications.

RESULTS

The desired geometrical and morphological aspects of the produced honeycomb core variants were validated using Computed Tomography (CT) scans. Figure 6 displays scans of the reference configuration (1, top), phase-separated (2, middle), and foamed variants (3, bottom). The reference variant scan shows a consistent wall thickness of 0.23 mm. A tapering effect, caused by the vacuum thermoforming process, appears after the bending area and is visible in all variants. As expected, the reference core's material remains homogeneous. In the phase-separated and foamed variants, the distinct three-layer structure is clearly visible in the respective CT scans 2 and 3. This is due to the density difference between PPH (higher) and PPC (lower). The phase-separated variant's outer layers are 0.022 mm thick ($\approx 20\%$ of total thickness), while the foamed variant's outer layers are 0.016 mm thick ($\approx 22\%$ of total thickness). The cellular structure in the foamed variant is distinct. The extrusion process causes significant pore elongation, resulting in a more needle-shaped form rather than an ellipsoid. The average pore size is $90 \times 20 \times 250 \mu\text{m}^3$ (x, y, z). These CT images confirm that all three designed variants can be successfully manufactured in a production-like setting, validating their desired morphological characteristics.

Figure 6: CT scan of developed specimens' cross section

The nonlinear buckling analysis under compressive loading yielded effective normal stresses and normal strains for each element until failure, which are presented in the form of stress-strain curves (see Figure 7). Initially, all configurations exhibit a linear elastic response, characterized by a proportional increase in effective normal stress with increasing strain. Upon reaching a critical stress level, local or global buckling phenomena initiate within the structure, marked by the attainment of a maximum point on the curve. Beyond this peak, the structural stability is compromised, and nonlinear effects become dominant. The post-peak behavior is governed by a combination of progressive buckling-induced instabilities and, depending on the material response, plastic deformation within the cell walls. This results in a reduction of the effective normal stress with further strain. The reference variant, with its homogeneous material composition, exhibited a maximum stress of 1.5 MPa. In contrast, the various three-layer core configurations (with outer layer thicknesses of 10%, 33%, 50%, and 90% and equal core density of 80 kg/m^3) demonstrated significantly improved performance, achieving peak stresses ranging from 2.2 to 2.3 MPa. The highest peak stress was observed in the third variant, which incorporated a foamed middle layer, reaching a significant improvement up to 2.4 MPa.

Figure 7: Stress-strain curves under compressive loading in FEA with varying layer thickness ratio ($2x_A/B$)

Figure 8 displays an exemplary comparison of compression strength (in MPa) versus cell wall density (in kg/m^3). These results from experimental mechanical testing validate the significant improvements achieved by the new honeycomb core designs. The phase-separated design, featuring high-density outer layers and a low-density core, showed a 12% improvement in compression strength, increasing from 1.19 MPa for the reference non-foamed honeycomb core to 1.33 MPa. Further enhancing performance, the introduction of a foamed middle layer in the third variant led to a 22% increase in compression strength, achieving 1.45 MPa. Notably, the density of all tested specimens remained consistent within usual process variation, ranging from approximately 81 to 83 kg/m^3 . This confirms that the new designs maintain weight efficiency while substantially improving mechanical properties.

Figure 8: ThermHex honeycomb compression strength versus cell wall density

A comparison between the experimentally tested and numerically simulated compression strengths reveals an overestimation by the simulation. For the reference non-foamed honeycomb core, the average tested compression strength was 1.19 MPa, while the simulation yielded a higher value of 1.5 MPa, indicating an overestimation of 26%. Similarly, for the phase-separated variant, the tested compression strength was 1.33 MPa, compared to a simulated value of 2.0 MPa, representing an overestimation of 50%. The foamed variant also showed this trend, with a tested strength of 1.45 MPa and a simulated strength of 2.4 MPa, resulting in an overestimation of 65% (see Table 2).

		Reference	Phase separation	Foamed mid-layer
ρ	[kg/m ³]	82.57	81.01	82.90
$R_{m,real}$	[N/mm ²]	1.19	1.33	1.45
$R_{m,sim}$	[N/mm ²]	1.5	2.0	2.4
Δ	[%]	26	50	65

Table 2: Comparison of experimental and simulated compression strengths

DISCUSSION

The observed discrepancies between simulated and experimentally determined compression strengths highlight several areas for consideration and potential refinement in the numerical model. Firstly, a primary source of potential overestimation lies in the material property input for the simulation. The mechanical properties of the PPH and PPC utilized in the model were derived from standardized tension tests on virgin material specimens. This approach inherently does not fully account for the effects of the extrusion and elongation processes that the material undergoes during the manufacturing of the thin honeycomb foils. These processes are known to induce molecular orientation and potentially alter the mechanical properties in a way not captured by bulk virgin material testing, likely leading to a reduction in actual performance compared to theoretical values. More accurate testing methods specifically designed for thin-section foils, or an alternative approach to determine the in-situ material properties of the extruded and elongated film, would be highly desirable for improving simulation accuracy. Secondly, the geometrical idealization of the honeycomb core in the simulation presents another potential source of deviation. The numerical model assumes perfectly straight cell walls, uniform cell distances, and precise angles. In reality, the manufacturing process invariably introduces imperfections and defects within the cell walls. These real-world flaws can act as stress concentrators or local weak points, promoting premature buckling and thus contributing to the lower experimental compression strengths compared to the idealized simulated performance. Future simulation efforts could benefit from incorporating representative manufacturing imperfections into the geometric model. This modification together with boundary conditions that not only allow for idealized z-direction displacement of the nodes, but also more realistic secondary in-plane-displacements can reduce the delta observed between testing and FEA. Other potential influences can include the imperfect test environment leading to uneven loading in flatwise compression tests if the load plates are not perfectly parallel. Despite these quantitative discrepancies, the parametric nature of the simulation model enables effective qualitative differentiation between variations in material properties and the relative proportions of outer and inner layers. This functionality provides a robust framework for informing design strategies, supporting the optimization of material selection and structural configurations during early-stage development and prototyping, even in the absence of precise numerical agreement with experimental results. The increasing delta of simulation vs. experiment for more challenging to produce configurations also hint at further improvement potential with more fine tuned manufacturing processes thereof.

The present investigation demonstrates that thermoplastic honeycomb cores can be significantly enhanced through sandwich-style cell wall structures, improving both mechanical performance and weight efficiency. Phase-separated and foamed middle-layer designs exhibit substantial gains in compression strength – 12% and 22% increases, respectively – without significant density variation.

This approach offers a notable advancement in enhancing structural performance without additional weight, critical for industries where material mass is a key design constraint. A salient advantage of this development is its recyclability. Exclusive utilization of thermoplastic materials without fiber reinforcement ensures uncompromised recyclability. This directly aligns with sustainability objectives by facilitating straightforward end-of-life recycling processes. First samples following a closed-loop approach by using post-consumer regranulate in the inner layer have already been manufactured in another coextrusion project by ThermHex. Consequently, these innovations position the novel honeycomb core configurations as highly promising for high-performance, lightweight applications, particularly within the automotive industry. Their synergistic combination of enhanced mechanical strength, consistent low density, and excellent recyclability presents significant potential for reducing vehicle mass, improving fuel efficiency, and contributing to more sustainable manufacturing.

CONCLUSION

This investigation successfully demonstrates that advanced thermoplastic honeycomb cores can be significantly enhanced through innovative sandwich cell wall structures, leading to improved mechanical performance and weight efficiency. The research explored three key variants: a monolayer reference, a phase-separated design, and a foamed mid-layer configuration. Significant performance gains were achieved with the new designs. The phase-separated variant showed a 12% increase in compression strength (from 1.19 MPa to 1.33 MPa), while the foamed mid-layer design delivered an even more remarkable 22% increase (reaching 1.45 MPa) compared to the reference. Crucially, these improvements were accomplished while maintaining a consistently low density across all tested samples (approx. 81-83 kg/m³), confirming their weight efficiency. Numerical simulations further supported these findings, predicting peak stresses up to 2.4 MPa for the idealized foamed variant. The feasibility of continuous production for all three variants was validated using the established production process at company ThermHex, Germany. Computed Tomography (CT) scans confirmed the successful creation of the desired morphological properties in a production-like environment. A major sustainability advantage of these materials lies in their uncompromised recyclability, stemming from the exclusive use of thermoplastics without fiber reinforcement. This characteristic aligns with sustainability goals by enabling straightforward end-of-life recycling, making these novel honeycomb cores highly promising for lightweight applications, particularly in the automotive industry, to reduce vehicle mass and improve fuel efficiency or allow for compensation of heavier electronics integration.

However, challenges in production and reproducibility were identified. A notable discrepancy was observed between simulated and experimental compression strengths, with simulations overestimating results by 26% to 65%. This overestimation is primarily attributed to using virgin material properties in simulations, which do not fully account for the effects of extrusion and elongation processes on thin foils, as well as idealized geometrical models and boundary conditions not reflecting real-world manufacturing and test setup imperfections. Despite these quantitative differences, the parametric simulation model remains valuable for qualitative differentiation and early-stage design optimization. Future work will focus on further developing hierarchical or hybrid designs to continuously optimize the properties of these advanced honeycomb core structures.

For future industrial implementation, further research and development efforts are essential to optimize the reproducibility and consistency of the manufacturing process. As with the scaling of any novel material system, achieving stringent process control and minimizing variabilities in material distribution and cellular morphology will be critical for ensuring robust and predictable performance across larger production batches and enabling widespread adoption of these advanced honeycomb core designs.

REFERENCES

- [1] Dymriton, “Application of Honeycomb Sandwich Composite Materials in Automotive Exterior Parts - Dymriton Composites.” Accessed: Jun. 13, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.dymriton.com/application-of-honeycomb-sandwich-composite-materials-in-automotive-exterior-parts-tissu-fibre-de-carbone/>, <https://www.dymriton.com/application-of-honeycomb-sandwich-composite-materials-in-automotive-exterior-parts-tissu-fibre-de-carbone/>
- [2] G. P. Chirinda and S. Matope, “The Lighter the Better: Weight Reduction in the Automotive Industry and its Impact on Fuel Consumption and Climate Change,” Dec. 2020.
- [3] T. R. Neu, K. Heim, W. Seeliger, P. H. Kamm, and F. García-Moreno, “Aluminum Foam Sandwiches: A Lighter Future for Car Bodies,” *JOM*, vol. 76, no. 5, pp. 2619–2630, May 2024, doi: 10.1007/s11837-024-06460-2.
- [4] G. Refiadi, I. S. Aisyah, and J. P. Siregar, “Trends in Lightweight Automotive Materials for Improving Fuel Efficiency and Reducing Carbon Emissions,” *Automot. Exp.*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 78–90, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.31603/ae.v2i3.2984.
- [5] J. Njuguna, *Lightweight composite structures in transport: design, manufacturing, analysis and performance*. in Woodhead Publishing series in composites science and engineering. Oxford: Woodhead Publishing, 2016.
- [6] F. Del Pero, L. Berzi, A. Antonacci, and M. Delogu, “Automotive Lightweight Design: Simulation Modeling of Mass-Related Consumption for Electric Vehicles,” *Machines*, vol. 8, no. 3, p. 51, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.3390/machines8030051.
- [7] A. Kausar, I. Ahmad, S. A. Rakha, M. H. Eisa, and A. Diallo, “State-Of-The-Art of Sandwich Composite Structures: Manufacturing—to—High Performance Applications,” *J. Compos. Sci.*, vol. 7, no. 3, p. 102, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.3390/jcs7030102.
- [8] J. Galos, M. Sutcliffe, D. Cebon, and Golam Newaz, “Lightweighting road freight semi-trailers through the application of composites in trailer decking,” 2015, doi: 10.13140/RG.2.1.1115.3042.
- [9] I. C. Sukmaji, W. R. Wijang, S. Andri, K. Bambang, and T. Teguh, “Application of sandwich honeycomb carbon/glass fiber-honeycomb composite in the floor component of electric car,” presented at the International Conference on Engineering, Science and Nanotechnology 2016 (ICESNANO 2016), Solo, Indonesia, 2017, p. 030056. doi: 10.1063/1.4968309.
- [10] J. Pruez, S. Shoukry, G. Williams, and M. Shoukry, “Lightweight Composite Materials for Heavy Duty Vehicles,” None, 1116021, Aug. 2013. doi: 10.2172/1116021.
- [11] F. Zerling and R. Zarnekow, “Increasing the efficiency and performance of thermoplastic honeycomb cores through co-extruded foam core sandwich cell walls,” presented at the 8th International Conference on Cellular Material (CellMAT 2024), Magdeburg, Germany, Nov. 2024.
- [12] J. Pflug, F. Zerling, R. Schlimper, and T. Gläßer, “Continuous Production of Thermoplastic Honeycomb Sandwich Panels for Thermoformed and Functionalized Automotive Parts,” presented at the 13th International Conference on Sandwich Structures (ICSS-13), Knoxville - USA, Oct. 2022.
- [13] J. Pflug, B. Vangrimde, I. Verpoest, and P. Bratfisch, “Honeycomb Core Materials: New Concepts for Continuous Production,” *Sampe J.*, vol. 39, Sep. 2003.